

Disorders of energy metabolism, protein and macronutrient metabolism in children with congenital heart defects

Rabbimova Dilfuza Toshtemirovna

MD, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Propaedeutics of Children's Diseases
Samarkand State Medical University Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Khalilova Manizha Abdurashidovna

Master of the Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract. *Nutritional deficiency is identified in various types of congenital heart defects, both "blue" and "pale" types. I. Arodiwe et al. [1] in a study of 40,123 children identified 50 with congenital heart defects; 46 (92%) of them had nutritional status changes of varying severity. According to WHO definition, nutritional deficiency ("nutritional insufficiency") is a cellular imbalance between the nutrients and energy provided by food and the body's need for them to ensure vital functions, growth, and specific functions [11, 4].*

Key words: *congenital heart defects, trophic deficiency, nutritional insufficiency, metabolism, protein requirements, breast milk, infant formula.*

Introduction.

The American Society for Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition (ASPEN) proposed an extended interpretation of nutritional deficiency as an imbalance between the need for nutrients and their intake, leading to a combined deficit of energy, protein, and micronutrients, which can negatively affect child growth, development, and have other adverse consequences [5, 7].

Trophic deficiency in such patients develops as a result of reduced nutrient intake combined with increased need for them. It has been found that in patients with ventricular septal defect, total energy expenditure is 40% higher than in children with normal heart anatomy [1]. Increased energy demand can occur with increased afterload on the right or left ventricles of the heart, such as in aortic coarctation or developing pulmonary hypertension, as well as in congenital heart failure. Accelerated metabolic processes in the myocardium are accompanied by increased oxygen and nutrient demand [1].

According to B.A. Hassan et al. [2], patients with congenital heart defects and developing heart failure require more energy to maintain enhanced myocardial function, respiratory tract function, and activation of neurohumoral regulation processes. Additionally, recurrent respiratory infections associated with chronic heart failure require increased metabolic exchange [2, 3]. The severity of energy imbalance in children with congenital heart defects, according to J.J. Wong et al. [4], is determined by the patient's age, type of cardiovascular pathology, and presence or absence of heart failure.

A study by I. Arodiwe et al. [1] showed that severe trophic deficiency is more common in patients with "blue" heart defects than in those with "pale" defects; minor nutritional status changes are found in patients without cyanosis and in the absence of pulmonary hypertension. An additional factor contributing to the development of trophic deficiency in children with heart defects is hypoxia, leading to compensated metabolic acidosis. Chronic hypoxemia exacerbates anorexia and contributes to insufficient nutrient absorption at the cellular level [1], impairs cellular metabolism, and cell growth [2].

Alteration of nutritional status can also be facilitated by impaired digestion and absorption processes in various parts of the gastrointestinal tract due to developing mesenteric hypoperfusion [1]. Researchers note that patients who have undergone surgery for congenital heart disease are at an increased risk of developing trophic insufficiency. Contributing factors in this case include the surgical intervention itself, anesthesia and infusion therapy, as well as postoperative care characteristics [4]. There is evidence that the development of trophic insufficiency leads to increased mortality in the perioperative period.

According to M. Radman et al. [6], reduced body weight, acute and chronic trophic insufficiency are associated with an increased incidence of adverse outcomes in cardiac surgery. In the absence of timely surgical correction of congenital heart disease, chronic hypoxemia persists, heart failure progresses, which contributes to the aggravation of nutritional status disorders [7].

According to B.A. Hassan's study [2], the severity of trophic insufficiency in children with congenital heart disease positively correlates with low hemoglobin levels, low blood oxygen saturation, the presence of heart failure, and the degree of pulmonary hypertension. Changes in nutritional status are associated with increased morbidity, frequent hospitalizations, changes in physical development, and increased mortality.

According to J. Slicker et al.'s recommendations [26], enteral nutrition can be used in patients with congenital heart disease and stable hemodynamics with adequate monitoring. For enteral feeding, it is proposed to use a nasogastric tube. Patients with an established umbilical catheter are recommended to receive enteral feeding. For patients with congenital heart disease with systemic duct-dependent circulation during prostaglandin infusion, enteral feeding is also recommended. Breast milk is preferable for enteral feeding due to its numerous nutritional and immune properties, the presence of easily absorbable protein with high biological value [26].

Due to the higher energy requirement in patients with hemodynamically significant congenital heart disease, breast milk, as the sole source of nutrients, often cannot be an optimal feeding product in terms of ensuring normal growth. To correct nutritional status in children with congenital heart disease, it is recommended to use breast milk and, if necessary, use its enrichers to increase its calorie content to 80–90 kcal/kg; use semi-elemental formulas enriched with medium-chain triglycerides (0.67 kcal/ml, 1–1.5 kcal/ml); increase feeding frequency or feed through a tube or increase the concentration of the formula; early introduction of complementary foods (from 4 months of life); and in children with clinical manifestations of heart failure, use formulas with low sodium content [28].

To date, there are no methods available for assessing the nutritional status of patients with CHF that have 100% sensitivity and reliability. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis is crucial, including anthropometric, laboratory, clinical, and functional research methods.

Currently, there are no unified nutritional protocols for children with CHF that would allow assessing nutritional deficiencies and prescribing effective nutritional support to ensure adequate energy, macro- and micronutrient intake [7, 34].

M.L. Forchielli et al. presented nutritional recommendations for children with CHD in the postoperative period, according to which standard energy requirements ranged from 75 to 120 kcal/kg/day and increased by 20-100% in the presence of stress, surgery, or malnutrition. The authors also emphasized the need to restrict fluid and salt intake, and stipulated that protein should constitute 8-10% of total caloric intake, carbohydrates and fats 35-50% and 35-60%, respectively [83].

In 2011, dietitians and cardiologists from the University of Virginia (USA) proposed an algorithm for nutritional support for infants with congenital heart defects, based on which, to ensure "catch-up"

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

growth, energy requirements should be 120-150 kcal/kg/day, and protein requirements 3-3.5 g/kg/day [12].

However, nutritional correction in some children with CHD does not lead to the desired effect due to the impossibility of consuming age-appropriate food volumes by patients [27]. Jackson and Poskitt (1991) proposed enriching nutrition (including breast milk) with glucose polymers, thereby increasing average energy intake by 31.7%, which led to an increase in body weight from 1.3 g/kg/day to 5.8 g/kg/day [13].

Traditionally, biochemical research methods are used to assess nutritional status disorders, including determination of serum levels of total protein, albumin, prealbumin (transthyretin), somatomedin-C, transferrin, and C-reactive protein [9].

Albumin is characterized as an acute-phase protein, and its concentration is influenced by the presence of inflammation, the use of drugs that impair liver function. For example, it was noted that low albumin levels are detected in liver failure, burns, sepsis, trauma, postoperative period, and oncological diseases [59]. It is known that albumin level can be a marker of nutritional status in patients after heart transplantation.

Another acute-phase protein synthesized in the liver is prealbumin. Its concentration in blood serum also changes during inflammatory/infectious conditions and liver diseases. There are several key differences between albumin and prealbumin: the half-life of prealbumin is significantly shorter and составляет 2-3 days, and its total reserve in the body is much less than albumin. These two factors theoretically allow using prealbumin levels as a more reliable indicator of acute changes in patients' nutritional status. However, due to the fact that prealbumin is excreted by the kidneys, any dysfunction of these organs leads to an increase in the level of this protein in blood serum. Transferrin is also an acute-phase protein used for diagnosing nutritional deficiency [13]. Inaccuracies in interpreting results arise due to transferrin's involvement in iron transport in blood, and its concentration increases in iron-deficiency anemia.

Thus, changes in serum levels of proteins such as albumin, prealbumin, and transferrin characterize the presence of an inflammatory process but do not reflect the severity of nutritional deficiency [133].

In S.R. Biryukova's study (2013), catabolic changes were identified in children with CHD in the early postoperative period, manifested by a decrease in total protein and albumin. In 62.5% of infants under one year of age and 37.9% of children aged 1 to 3 years, a decrease in IGF-1 levels was observed. At the same time, the administration of nutritional support using semi-elemental formulas in patients with CHD allowed for improved protein synthesis indicators by the 5th postoperative day, reduced systemic inflammation activity, and a trend towards improved somatometric parameters [21, 22]. To determine the tactics of dietary treatment for patients with nutritional deficiency, the severity of body weight and height deficit is established, the main causes of physical development disorders are identified, and the child's actual diet is analyzed. An important indicator of the adequacy of prescribed therapeutic nutrition is weight gain. The optimal weight gain for an infant in the first year of life is considered to be 20-30 g/day. Gradually, from the age of 4 months, patients with CHF are introduced to complementary foods, with a preference given to energy-dense products - industrial baby cereals, for dilution of which therapeutic formulas are used. Special attention is paid to sufficient content of meat puree, vegetables, fruits, and vegetable oils in diets [11, 12].

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, it is clearly visible that nutritional deficiency in children with CHF requires close attention and correction, as it can lead to both short-term and long-term consequences. Children with congenital heart disease and nutritional deficiency in the preoperative period are predisposed to frequent infectious complications; due to low body weight, they receive life-saving surgical treatment in a timely manner; in the postoperative period, such patients are prone to longer wound healing, prolonged stay in the intensive care unit, which prolongs hospitalization, and in severe cases, increases the risk of mortality [9].

It has now been proven that breast milk is the optimal easily digestible source of nutrients, possesses pronounced protective properties due to the presence of immunoglobulins, macrophages, lactoferrin, lysozyme, oligosaccharides, bifidobacteria and lactobacilli, growth factors, hormones, and also serves as the most important factor in programming human health in later life [18, 22]. Since breast milk is the gold standard for feeding an infant in the first year of life, in the nutrition of 20 (42%) breastfed children, it was tried to preserve maternal milk as much as possible. In case of severe symptoms of chronic heart failure, such as tachypnea, weakness, severe loss of appetite, difficulty in sucking milk from the mother's breast, poor sleep, the child was fed with expressed breast milk from a bottle, and in severe condition - through a tube. The required volume of breast milk and feeding frequency were calculated for each child individually, taking into account, according to the recommendations of the Association of Pediatric Cardiologists of Russia, the forced limitation of daily fluid intake and norms of physiological energy and protein requirements [7, 8, 28].

Thus, it has been established that achieving optimal energy and essential nutrient provision for a sick infant in the first six months of life with cardiomyopathy or congenital heart disease complicated by CHF and nutritional deficiency is possible only by using specialized enteral nutrition products. At the same time, in infants on natural feeding, these products should be combined with the maximum possible proportion of breast milk. For patients older than 4 months, in order to increase the energy value of the diet and enrich it with micronutrients, complementary foods (baby cereals, vegetable, meat, fruit puree, cottage cheese, vegetable and butter oils) were gradually added to breast milk or a specialized formula [11, 12].

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Congenital anomalies. World Health Organization; September 2016: 193–195. <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs370/en/>.
3. Мутафьян О. А. Пороки сердца у детей и подростков. Руководство для врачей. М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа; 2009. 560 с. [Mutaf'yan O. A. Poroki serdtsa u detei i podrostkov. Rukovodstvo dlya vrachei. M.: GEOTAR-Media; 2009. 560 s. (in Russian)].
4. Бокерия Л. А., ред. Клинические рекомендации по ведению детей с врожденными пороками сердца. М.: НЦССХ им. А. Н. Бакулева; 2014. 342 с. [Bokeriya L. A., red. Klinicheskie rekomendatsii po vedeniyu detei s vrozhdannymi porokami serdtsa. M.: NTsSSKh im. A. N. Bakuleva; 2014. 342 s. (in Russian)].
5. Шарыкин А. С. Врожденные пороки сердца: проблемы плода и новорожденного ребенка. Consilium Medicum. 2012; 3: 54–8. [Sharykin A. S. Vrozhdannye poroki serdtsa: problemy ploda i novorozhdennogo rebenka. Consilium Medicum. 2012; 3: 54–8. (in Russian)].
6. Кудаяров Д. К., Муратов А. А., Мусуркулова Б. А., Болотбекова А. Ж., Бакаева А. К. Врожденные пороки сердца у детей: структура, причинные факторы, клинические проявления. Вестн. Кыргызско-Российского славянского университета. 2016; 16(11): 40–2.

- [Kudayarov D. K., Muratov A. A., Musurkulova B. A., Bolotbekova A. Zh., Bakaeva A. K. Vrozhdennyye poroki serdtsa u detei: struktura, prichinnye faktory, klinicheskie proyavleniya. Vestn. Kyrgyzsko-Rossiiskogo slavyanskogo universiteta. 2016; 16(11): 40–2. (in Russian)].
7. Фролова Н. И., Белокриницкая Т. Е., Страмбовская Н. Н. Молекулярно-генетические предикторы осложнений беременности у молодых здоровых женщин. Дальневосточный медицинский журнал. 2015; 3: 29–30. [Belokrinitskaya T. E., Frolova N. I., Strambovskaya N. N. Molekulyarno-geneticheskie prediktory oslozhnenij beremennosti u molodyh zdorovyh zhenshchin. Dal'nevostochnyj medicinskij zhurnal. 2015; 3: 29–30. (in Russian)].
8. Лиманова О. А., Торшин И. Ю., Сардарян И. С., Калачева А. Г., Хабабпасhev А., Карпучин Д. и др. Обеспеченность микронутриентами и женское здоровье: интеллектуальный анализ клинико-эпидемиологических данных. Вопр. гинекологии, акушерства и перинатологии. 2014; 13(2): 5–15. [Limanova O. A., Torshin I. Yu., Sardaryan I. S., Kalacheva A. G., Hababpashev A., Karpuchin D. i dr. Obespechennost' mikronutrientami i zhenskoe zdorov'e: intellektual'nyi analiz kliniko-epidemiologicheskikh dannykh. Vopr. ginekologii, akusherstva i perinatologii. 2014; 13(2): 5–15. (in Russian)]
9. Боровик Т.Э., Гандаева Л.А., Басаргина Е.Н., Звонкова Н.Г. Недостаточность питания у детей с заболеваниями сердца. // Вопросы питания. 2014; 83 (3):108-109.
10. Гандаева Л.А., Боровик Т.Э., Басаргина Е.Н., Звонкова Н.Г. Возможности коррекции нутритивного статуса у детей с врожденными пороками сердца. // Казанский медицинский журнал. 2015; 96 (4): 654-659 с.
11. Гандаева Л.А., Боровик Т.Э., Басаргина Е.Н., Звонкова Н.Г. Актуальность оценки нутритивного статуса у детей с хронической сердечной недостаточностью. // Вопросы современной педиатрии. 2015; 14 (6):699- 705.
12. Синнес А. Последствия врожденных пороков сердца для развития нервной системы: влияние, факторы риска и патофизиология. Журнал детской кардиологии и кардиохирургии. 2017; 1:28-36.
13. Марино Б.С., Липкин П.Х., Ньюбургер Дж.У. и др. Результаты развития нервной системы у детей с врожденными пороками сердца: оценка и ведение: научное заявление Американской ассоциации сердца. Кровообращение. 2012;126:1143–72.
14. Акрамова Х. А. Нейроспецифический белок S100b в прогнозе нарушений раннего неонатального периода у новорожденных //Educatio. – 2015. – №. 3 (10)-5.